

Deliverable:

**D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.5.1
and 5.2**

**Workshop: Facilitation and
communication of the
OHLabCap**

**Workshop: Joint workshop
between CARE, OH-HARMONY-
CAP, and MATRIX**

**Workpackage 5 of OH-
Harmony-Cap: Project
Coordination**

Responsible Partner: P13-SSI

Contributing partners: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-
SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA.

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.5.1 AND 5.2 WORKSHOP: FACILITATION AND COMMUNICATION OF THE OHLABCAP WORKSHOP: JOINT WORKSHOP BETWEEN CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, AND MATRIX

Background

JIP4-WP5-T1 Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap

The final workshop was held in Copenhagen, on September 21st – 22nd for the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium. Each WP was discussed with overall focus on identification of gaps, recommendations, and dissemination of OH-HARMONY-CAP. The overall consensus; 1) the consortium was very pleased with the usefull outcomes and contributions from all WPs particular WP3, WP4, and WP5. 2) The development of OHLabCap proved difficult, particularly the formulation of the 59 questions as the various sectors perceives and understand them differently. One recommendation would entail additional work and focus groups and several pilots before launching the OHLabCap monitoring tool again as discussed in the final deliverable.

JIP04-WP5.T2 Joint workshop between CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX

The three projects jointly held their final meetings on September 20th 2022 in Copenhagen. Highlights from the three projects were presented. The meeting ended with a final roundtable where representatives of JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX, the OHEJP Project Management Team and OHEJP Stakeholders participated. During that discussion the below following was discussed and highlighted:

- The JIPs have now concluded and delivered and sustainability of the JIP depends on those who can utilize and advance the generated knowledge and outputs. This is an opportunity of not just partner institutions but also countries and stakeholders
- Social sciences are key to ensure a change (in the direction of One Health) that necessarily requires a change in the knowledge, attitudes and practices of many across different sectors and at different levels of the decision making process
- Studying the cost-effectiveness of One Health is an opportunity to secure the necessary attention that the approach requires.

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Please find agenda below

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OHEJP JIPs CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP
Grant Agreement number 773830

September 20, 2022

Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark

Attendees: Project Consortia and invitees (in person only)

September 20, 2022, times are CEST

Location: Gymnastiksalen. Building 216A

09.00-09.20	Arrival and welcome
09.20-09.30	Introduction to the meeting Rene S. Hendriksen – DTU National Food Institute, JIP CARE Nadia Boisen – Statens Serum Institut, JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP Guido Benedetti – Statens Serum Institut, JIP MATRIX
09.30-09.50	Keynote – The relevance of OHEJP Joint Integrative Projects from a Danish perspective – 15min-P + 5min-Q Kåre Mølbak – Statens Serum Institut
09.50-10.10	Keynote – The relevance of OHEJP Joint Integrative Projects from an international perspective – 15min-P + 5min-Q Karin Artursson – Swedish National Veterinary Institute, OHEJP WP4
10.10-10.30	Keynote – The future of the One Health European Joint Programme and opportunities for countries – 15min-P + 5min-Q Hein Imberechts – Sciensano, OHEJP PMT
10.30-11.00	Break
11.00-11.20	Keynote – One Health Surveillance in Europe: what do we need from a food safety perspective – 15min-P + 5min-Q Stef Bronzwaer – European Food Safety Authority
11.20-12.20	OH-HARMONY-CAP – 45min-P + 15min-Q
12.20-13.30	Lunch
13.30-14.30	CARE – 45min-P + 15min-Q
14.30-15.30	MATRIX – 45min-P + 15min-Q
15.30-16.00	Break
16.00-16.45	Round table – The legacy of Joint Integrative Projects Chair: Pikka Jokelainen, Statens Serum Institut
16.45-17.00	Closure Rene S. Hendriksen – DTU National food Institute, JIP CARE Nadia Boisen – Statens Serum Institut, JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP Guido Benedetti – Statens Serum Institut, JIP MATRIX
18.00-21.00	Social dinner

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OHEJP OH-HARMONY-CAP
Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark

Attendees: Project Consortia (in person only)

September 21, 2022, times are CEST

Location: Lecture hall (Foredræssalen) Building 42B/219

09.00-09.15	<i>Arrival and coffee</i>
09.00-09.20	Comments from the meeting with CARE and MATRIX Nadia Bolan and Flemming Sobutz - Statens Serum Institut, JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP
	Summary and outputs from Work packages
09.20-10.30	WP2: Flemming Sobutz - Statens Serum Institut (SSI) Lin Brandal and Umair Naseer - Norwegian Institute of Public Health (FHI) Catarina Fjell - Swedish Food Agency (SLV) María Aybar-Espinoza - Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)
10.30 - 10.40	<i>Break</i>
10.40 - 11.30	WP3: Deolan Bolton - The Agriculture and Food Development Authority (Teagasc) Mónica Queiroz - The National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA) Miranda Kirchner - Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)
11.30 - 12.00	WP4: Boriana Tezzoli - Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) Melanie Gay - French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) Mirek Rozycki - Polish National Veterinary Research Institute
12.00-13.00	<i>Lunch</i> Statens Serum Institut (SSI)
13.00 - 13.30	WP4: Boriana Tezzoli - Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) Melanie Gay - French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) Mirek Rozycki - Polish National Veterinary Research Institute
13.30 - 14.00	WP5: Fabio Tocini - Italian National Institute of Health (ISS)
14.00-14.30	Group work <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main outcome • Identification of gaps • Conclusion
14.30-14.45	<i>Break - coffee</i>
14.45-16.15	Group work <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main outcome • Identification of gaps • Conclusion
17.00-20.00	<i>Social dinner with CARE</i>

OHEJP JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP final meeting

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OHEJP OH-HARMONY-CAP
Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark

Attendees: Project Consortia (in person only)

September 22, 2022, times are CEST

Location: Lecture hall (Foredragsalen) Building 42B/219

08.45 - 09.00	Arrival and coffee
09.00 - 10.00	Group work presentations
	Group work:
10.00-10.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendation • Dissemination of OH-HARMONY-CAP
10.30 - 10.45	Break - coffee
	Group work:
10.45 - 11.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendation • Dissemination of OH-HARMONY-CAP
11.30-12.00	What's next: end of OH-HARMONY-CAP Nadja Bolcen - Statens Serum Institut (SSI)